

The Inclusion and Mainstreaming of the Active Role of Women in Peacemaking, Conflict Resolution, Reconciliation, Peacebuilding, Recovery, and Reconstruction: Lessons Learned and Best Practices from the Field¹

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INTRODUCTION

Problem Statement

In general, women are neglected in research, which is problematic, leading to gaps in the literature about the challenges and their contributions to social change. Hence, using feminist epistemology, this paper aims to fill the gaps in the literature and provide policy recommendations for the more inclusive participation of women as active players in social transformation in conflict-affected areas.

Research Questions

To unpack the research gaps about the roles of women, this paper answers the following research questions:

1. What is the conflict situation in the southern Philippine island of Mindanao?
2. What is the impact of the armed conflict on women?
3. What are the barriers to the full participation of women to conflict transformation and peacebuilding?
4. What are the roles women play in negotiation, reconciliation, peacebuilding, recovery, and reconstruction?
5. What are some case studies of women and men engaging in peacebuilding?
6. What are the best practices and lessons learned that can be used to pave the way for the more inclusive participation of women in the management, resolution, and transformation of conflict?

Objectives of the Study

This paper examines the conflict in the southern Philippines. The objectives of this paper are the following:

1. To give an overview of the conflict situation in Mindanao in order to contextualize peacebuilding and reconstruction work;
2. To find out what the impact of the armed conflict on women;

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3. To identify the barriers to the full participation of women to conflict transformation and peacebuilding;
4. To explain the roles women play in negotiation, reconciliation, peacebuilding, recovery, and reconstruction;
5. To highlight case studies of women and men who are engaged in peacebuilding; and,
6. To share the best practices and lessons learned that can be used to pave the way for the more inclusive participation of women in the management, resolution, and transformation of conflict

Definition of Terms

To have a common understanding of the key terms used in this paper, the following words are defined here: conflict management, conflict resolution, conflict transformation, negotiation, reconciliation, peacebuilding, peacemaking, recovery, and reconstruction.

1. **Conflict management** is a kind of game that people “play” in real life, after two sides have disagreements. It refers to the styles one uses to deal with conflict. They include avoidance (lose-win), compromise (win-win), sacrificing oneself (lose-win), and confrontation (win-lose).
2. **Conflict resolution** here refers to pacific methods of stopping discord between two sides. Article 33 of the Charter of the United Nations (1945) identify these methods as negotiation, enquiry, mediation, conciliation, arbitration, regional arrangements, and good offices.
3. By **conflict transformation** is meant a transformation of relationships, not just the absence of physical or overt violence (Galtung, 1996). It is the process of constructive change (Lederach, 2003). It involves comprehensive, pro-active, long-term, social-justice-related measures and actions on the levels of “direct interaction and social structures,” which deal with the social and political roots of hostilities which promote change (Lederach, 2003, p. 14). The aim of conflict transformation is the reduction of violence, the increase in justice, and a response to real-world social problems (Lederach, 2003).
4. **Negotiation** is a type of pacific conflict resolution method in which the two parties to a discord talk directly to each other.
5. “The term ‘**Peacebuilding**’ first emerged in 1970s through the work of Johan Galtung who called for the creation of peacebuilding structures to promote sustainable peace by addressing the “root causes” of violent conflict and supporting indigenous capacities for peace management and conflict resolution. Since then, the term Peacebuilding has covered a multidimensional exercise and tasks ranging from the disarming of warring factions to the rebuilding of political, economic, judicial and civil society institutions” (United Nations, 2014). A comparison of the definition of peacebuilding and conflict transformation reveals that they are very closely related, if not synonymous.
6. **Peacemaking** refers to “the search for a negotiated resolution of the perceived conflicts of interests between the parties” (Ryan, 1995, p. 106). It involves political and diplomatic activity to reach a reconciliation of perceived conflicts of interests (Ryan, 1995). Note, that peacemaking sounds like a generic umbrella term that can be synonymous with the term conflict resolution, of which there are many methods.
7. **Reconciliation** refers to two sides, once at odds with one another, decide to forgive each other and have amicable relations once again from this moment onward.

8. **Recovery** refers to the restoration more or less to the same level of how things were prior to negative changes (such as armed conflict) in everything: economic livelihood, psychological state of mind, political stability, and so on.
9. **Reconstruction** means to rebuild things which have been lost, such as due to armed hostilities. It could refer to building new edifices or to recreating new lives, so to speak, after the conflict has ended.

LITERATURE REVIEW

When we talk about **gender**, we are not only talking about the female or male sex only. Rather, we are talking about what roles women and men play actually play and are expected to play. Is political participation gender-specific? What is the “ideal” gender role for women and men in political participation and involvement decision making? Who decides on these matters? Here, we are talking about power, when we talk about question of participation and decision making (IA, 2007 August). Gender refers to “the roles and relationships, attitudes, behaviours and values that society ascribes to men and women and to the relationships between women and men” (IHRICON & Saferworld, 2011). Society and culture change through time. So can we—women and men—decide to change gender roles as well. Gender inclusion and integration strengthen local ownership (Barnes & Albrecht, 2008, p. 3) in post-conflict countries, transitional and developing countries, and developed countries. Note, however, that gender roles are very complex.

Gender-based violence (GBV) refers to violence that is inflicted as a result of the inequalities between women and men, violating the fundamental right to life, liberty, security of the person, dignity, equality, equality between the sexes, non-discrimination, as well as physical and psychological integrity (Rojas, 2014). As a result, **gender equity** policies are put in place to compensate for the disadvantages between the sexes (Rojas, 2014). The ultimate aim is **gender equality**, which will be achieved when women’s rights become full human rights in policies, programs, and practice, accounting for the intersectionality of class, age, gender, regional, ethnic, and other differences (Rojas, 2014).

According to International Alert, there are **three models** of the role of gender in peace-building (El-Bushra, 2012; Myrntinen, Naujoks, & El-Bushra, 2014, p. 25): (1) “gender-blind,” which has been the norm for a long time; (2) gender-aware (Adrian-Paul & Naderi, 2005, pp. 16, 26, 27), gender-sensitive, or “WPS-focused,” [referring to women, peace, and security], which is gaining more and more traction; and, (3) “gender-relational,” the last being the most unrepresented. Gender is relational, “because masculine and female identities are created in relationship with each other, within the context of the whole society” (IA, 2013, p. 5). The relational approach to gender means that “gender roles and identities” are “being constructed through the power relations between men, women, and sexual and gender minorities – as well as through the power relations within these groups. Gender identities, roles and expectations do not exist in separation from other identity markers, such as class, age, marital status, disability, sexuality and the like, but are closely tied to these” (Myrntinen, Naujoks, & El-Bushra, p. 8). There is a need to engage “with the intersections between various identity markers and what they mean for peace-building” (p. 11).

To stereotype all women as the same, such as “victims,” and that all men are the same, “aggressors,” is counterproductive. **New approaches** include (1) the understanding of masculini-

ties and “the potential of **new masculinity roles** for peacebuilding” and (2) **gender-synchronized approaches** (Greene & Levack, 2010) which involve “the intentional intersection of gender-transformative efforts reaching both men and boys and women and girls of all sexual orientations and gender identities. They engage people in challenging harmful and restrictive constructions of masculinity and femininity that drive gender-related vulnerabilities and inequalities and hinder health and well-being” (Rojas, 2014).

The **United Nations** mainstreams gender in peacebuilding through the passage of many resolutions, namely: U.N. Resolution 1325 (2000) and the subsequent Resolution 1888 on gender-based violence; Resolution 1888 on sexual violence; Resolution 1889 on women in post-conflict reconstruction; Resolution 1960 on sexual violence in conflict; and Resolution 2122 on the rule of law and transitional justice (Rojas, 2014).

Lessons from **Guinea, Liberia, and Sierra Leone** show that to implement United Nations Resolution 1325, the following have to be taken into consideration: (1) “Working (better) with what exists: Engage custodians of the customary justice system” (Schoofs, Nagarajan, & Abebe, 2010, p. 5); (2) “Address sexual and gender-based violence: Mobilize communities through change agents” (p. 6); (3) “Economics matters: Address the economic dimension of gender, peace and security” (p. 7); and (4) “From plans to action: Make smart investments in civil society” (p. 8).

Lessons from **Nepal** reveal that to ensure inclusive participation, women and men must be representatives of local communities, attend and engage in activities of common concern (Johnston-Coeterier, 2014 January). Inclusive representation and participation are a matter of choice. “It is usually safest to go through existing power structures, to ensure that individuals approached later are not made vulnerable” (Johnston-Coeterier, 2014, p. 13). Inclusion (Johnston-Coeterier, 2014) must refer not only to people of different gender, but also “people of different ages, ethnicities,” (p. 15)... and “those who are illiterate/less literate” (p. 16) “that are representative of the local community” (p. 15).

Additionally lessons can be learned from **Rwanda**, where the Constitution stipulates that a certain proportion of women must be represented in public office. The Constitution of Rwanda has a quota for female representation in politics: ‘The State of Rwanda commits itself that women are granted at least 30 per cent of posts in decision making organs’ (Constitution, Article 9 [4]). Furthermore, the electoral law stipulates: “Twenty four (24) female Deputies shall be elected by specific organs in accordance with national administrative entities. A Presidential Order shall determine a national administrative entity and the number of women Deputies to be elected at each entity. At each entity through which election has been conducted, candidates who obtain more votes shall be considered as elected’ (Article 109 of Organic Law 03/2010/OL of 18 June 2010 governing presidential and legislative elections).”

Lessons from **Burundi, Colombia, Nepal, and Uganda** show that, based on a gender perspective, four issues emerged as important in peacebuilding: (1) access to justice, (2) economic recovery of displaced persons, refugees, and former combatants, (3) intergenerational tensions and conflicts; and, (4) permutations and continuums of violence, such as “self-inflicted, interpersonal, domestic, sexual and gender-based, criminal, communal and political violence” (Myrntinen, Naujoks, & El-Bushra, 2014, p. 8).

Lessons from **Northern Uganda** demonstrate that post-conflict recovery efforts must support “women’s changing fortunes” and “gender-sensitive recovery” (IA, 2010, September, Issue No. 3, p. 46). One, recovery programming must reconceptualize “the role of women in... peace economy—moving beyond ‘vulnerability’ to recognize women as economic actors and

agents of social change;” acknowledge, analyze “and reflect in program design the critical role played by women in the livelihood economy,” “ensure efforts to promote recovery and development...are based on gender-sensitive context analysis;” “[t]rain local authorities and officials at district and sub-county levels in gender-sensitive planning and budgeting;” “[c]reate and fill posts for gender officers within local government where this has not been done;” “[i]ncrease space for women on the planning structures at all levels of local government, as well as consultation with women at the grassroots;” and “[d]evelop planning and monitoring tools for both conflict and gender impacts of interventions” (p. 6).

Gender must be made a core element in the design and implementation of recovery interventions (IA, 2010 September, p. 47). The “economic empowerment of women” must be a “part of building a peace economy” (pp. 6, 48). Measures include the following: to “[s]cale-up community infrastructure programmes, reducing obstacles to women’s economic participation;” “[i]mprove women’s access to markets and agricultural technology;” “[p]rovide women-friendly financial services;” prioritize “efforts to secure women’s rights to housing and land;” “[o]ffer business development services and skills transfer opportunities for women;” harmonize “use of group formation as a prerequisite for assistance for women;” and “[p]romote affirmative action for women in awarding of local government contracts.”

Three, “women’s political advancement” must be supported as well (p. 49). These measures include the following; to “[e]ncourage political confidence and engagement on local political issues within women’s groups;” “[t]rain women on assertiveness, campaign skills, public speaking, negotiation, lobbying, advocacy, fundraising and gender budgeting;” “[f]ind CSOs providing support to women to engage in political life and monitoring of recovery programmes;” “[m]obilize women and men to vote for women, and work with women MPs to promote women-focused politics;” and “[i]mplement a government action plan on women in peacebuilding” (IA, 2010, p. 7)

Four, there is a need to “[i]nvest in constructive social transformation” (IA, 2010, p. 8). Measures include the following: to “[b]uild opportunities to explore the transformation of gender roles and relations and incorporate them into the planning and implementation of all economic recovery interventions across the spectrum of programming;” “[i]ncrease community training on gender relations in order for men to better appreciate the role of women and see them as partners, rather than a threat to their masculinity;” “[s]cale-up the availability, inclusivity and impact of psycho-social recovery programmes across all groups;” “[s]cale-up sensitization programmes on VAW [violence against women] and increase the effectiveness of community policy;” and “[i]mplement the...Domestic Violence Act” for countries that have such an act or to propose the legislation of such an act for countries without one (p. 8).

In summary, each historical and social context is different. At the same time, there are many lessons we can learn from the best practices in different countries of Asia, Africa, and Latin America, as cited in the case studies in the literature review above. In the findings of this paper are lessons we can learn and also the best practices from the conflict-torn southern Philippines.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Using a qualitative research design, this research is a descriptive paper that uses empirical data to yield an inductively generated grounded theory. Data come from the study of the lived

experiences of women in conflict situations. I was the Training Coordinator of the International Training Office, Division of International Affairs of Northern Illinois University from 2004 to 2014 where I organized and conducted international trainers' training and where I have met many Muslim women from conflict areas. Muslims whom I personally know who are actively involved in community work were purposively selected as my research partners.

Site Selection and Comparative Case Studies. The study sample consists of case studies of Muslim and non-Muslim leaders in conflict-affected Mindanao and the Sulu Archipelago in the southern Philippines who are actively involved in conflict transformation and peacebuilding from which best practices and lessons learned can be gathered.

Research Data Collection Method. In response to a semi-structured interview schedule, verbal descriptions were collected to gain insights into the research collaborators' experiences and perspectives through their true-to-life voices (Krathwohl, 1993). I know all the research collaborators in this research papers, as I have met them all when I have worked at the Training Coordinator of the International Training Office of Northern Illinois University (NIU), except for one who is the spouse of someone whom I have also met at NIU in the same capacity. Aside from the interview schedule, I have also used archival documents that documented the work and activities of my research collaborators.

Narrative and Discourse Analysis. The voices of the research collaborators take center stage here. In response to the research questions, female research participants deconstruct, reconstruct, and narrate the socially constructed meanings of their personal experiences and the roles of other women as well. Their male counterparts talk about their observations regarding the roles that women and men play in conflict-torn places, providing comparative analysis about the roles of women and men in peacebuilding. Narrative reports from which quotes are extracted provide authentic authorial representation (Creswell, 1998, p. 15). My research collaborators share stories and I captured "the qualities of 'life as lived'" (Abu-Lughod, 1993, p. 2). Open-ended interviews, informal dialogues, narrative inquiry, and self-reports are used to obtain responses to open-ended or semi-structured items that depict women's perceptions, roles, and experiences.

Research Collaborators

Engaged in comparative analysis, the author of this paper is a male feminist who has continually been conducting countless comparative research about women's issues in Africa, Asia, Middle East, Latin America, and the U.S.A. on a host of issues. The research collaborators cited in this paper are all from the southern Philippine islands of Mindanao and the Sulu Archipelago, which has one of the longest running armed conflict in the world. They live in communities with uneven and varying degrees of conflict and non-conflict. Most of the research collaborators are Muslims and female. Male research collaborators share their insights about the comparative roles that women and men play in peacebuilding in the southern Philippines. One female Christian research collaborator shared her perceptions on the roles that Muslim and Christian women and men play in peacebuilding in the southern Philippines. There are other research collaborators whom I have contacted—indigenous and Muslim women and men—who could have added and further enriched insights into this paper. However, due to various reasons, they unfortunately could not take part in this research.

Female Research Collaborators. As of this writing, there are six female research collaborators, five of whom are Muslim and one Christian. They belong to different ethno-linguistic groups. Susana Salvador **Anayatin** has a Doctorate in Peace and Development. She is the only

Christian Tagalog research collaborator in this paper. She is very active in promoting a “Culture of Peace and Nonviolence” with ex-combatants, women, and students. She works at the Department of Trade and Industry – ARMM and teaches part-time graduate peace studies at two higher education institutions. She is also a partner of the Chicago-based Goldin Institute, focusing on women’s leadership conflict resolution, poverty alleviation, and environmental sustainability.

Sarah Jane **Diang** prefers to be called Sarah because Jane sounds Christian. She is half Maguindanao and half Ilongga. She is an instructor of Social Work at a state university in Mindanao. She lives in Dalican, Datu Odin Sinsuat, Maguindanao.

Elin Anisha **Guro** is ethnically a Maranao. She works at Mindanao State University and was a former committee member of the National Commission for Culture and the Arts.

Dahlia “Dahl” J. **Martin** is a Muslim Tausug. She has a bachelor’s degree in social work and is currently finishing her Master’s in social work at the University of Mindanao in Davao City. She works as a social worker in the Department of Social Welfare and Development Office Region XII. “My position is City Link in the program of Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program that aims for the economic and social development of poor Filipinos. I am awarded as best City Link and Best Speaker in Family Development Session. Helping the poor communities become self-sufficient and active citizenship. In the past, I am the Officer-In-Charge in the Third World Movement against the Exploitation of Women Gensan based for 8 years, wherein we help women and children survivors of incest, rape and other forms of exploitation for healing and renewal. I am also involved in peace advocacy with my late boss Sr. Soledad Perpinan, RGS by giving peace workshops of Paolo Freire’s Conscientizing Inquiry in conflict ridden areas all over Mindanao.”

Noriam H. **Ladjjagais** is a Muslim Tausug. She is a “a Guidance Coordinator at the Basilan National High School, a part-time commissioner in the Komisyon sa Wikang Filipino, representing the languages of the ARMM mainly the Tausug. Also a board member and secretary of Moro women network named “NISA UL-HAQQ Fi Bangsamoro, Inc.” that advocates and promotes the rights of Moro women particularly the Muslim women Islamic rights. The group is also engaged in environment protection, good governance ,peace process, RH& RR, that promote peaceful, gender sensitive and socio-economic development in the Bangsamoro land.”

Fatima “Faith” P. **Kanakan** is a half-Iranun and half-Teduray Muslim. She is the executive director of the Office for Southern Cultural Committee of the Autonomous Region of Muslim Mindanao (ARMM).

Male Research Collaborators. As of this writing, there are four male research collaborators, all of whom are Muslim. They give their opinions about the roles women can play in peacebuilding. They also shared information about what they are doing and provide insights and comparative analysis for the possibilities for female and male roles in peacebuilding. Abdul Hamidullah T. **Atar** is a Muslim Maranao who is an elected and enthroned Sultan of Marawi and his nickname is Pogie. He has two bachelor’s degrees from Mindanao State University: one in Public Affairs and another in Islamic Studies. He has a Master’s degree in Public Administration from the same university. He is the Executive Officer of RIDO Inc. in Lanao Province.

Nelson “Neldy” **Dino** is a Muslim Suluk/Tausug. He has a Bachelor of Science in Forestry from Mindanao State University in Marawi. He has worked as a lecturer at Mindanao State University in Sulu for 3 years. He has taken Master of Public Administration and Master of Science in Agriculture at Sulu State College. His engagement in the youth leadership development, arts, human rights and peace advocacy brought him to study governance at NCPAG, University

of the Philippines, Diliman. He is a traveller, an activist and photorista who spreads the message of peace by his art of poetry, theatre arts, and movie acting, immersing with locals and understanding cultural and socio-political dynamics among regions. Aside from speaking Bahasa Malaysia, Bahasa Sug and English, he also speaks Bisaya, Maranao, Surigaonun and Tagalog. His poems had been published internationally, in USA, Philippines and Malaysia. Aside from being a kahawarista or a coffee lover and coffee maker, he is currently a full time novelist, writer, and researcher.

Argie “Arg” J. **Sarco** is a Muslim with Tausug with Bisayan heritage. He is a college instructor, the Director for Student Affairs and Services, and concurrently the Coordinator of the Peace Center, all in Basilan State College in Isabela City. He is also a core group member of the Interfaith Council of Leaders (IFCL) and Vice President for External Affairs of United Youth for Peace and Development (UNYPAD) Basilan Chapter, which is a member of Mindanao Anti Torture Alliance.

Dr. Alzad **Sattar** is a Muslim of Sama, Yakan, and Tausug heritage. He received his Master’s degree from Brandeis University and his doctorate from Basilan State College. He is the Undersecretary for Madrasah Education of the Department of Education – ARMM. He is a coordinator of the Interfaith Council of Leaders in Basilan.

Table 1: Profiles of Research Collaborators

Number	Female/ Male	Last Name	First Name	Religion	Ethnicity	Profession
1.	F	Anayatin	Susana	Christian	Tagalog	NGO CEO
2.	F	Diang	Sarah	Islam	Maguindanao & Ilongga	Instructor
3.	F	Guro	Anisha	Islam	Maranao	University Administra- tor
4.	F	Kanakan	Fatima (Faith)	Islam	Iranun & Teduray	Director
5.	F	Ladjajagais	Noriam	Islam	Tausug	Guidance counselor & NGO
6.	F	Martin	Dahlia	Islam	Tausug	Social Worker
7.	M	Atar	Hamidullah (Pogie)	Islam	Maranao	NGO CEO
8.	M	Dino	Nelson	Islam	Tausug	Instructor & Artist
9.	M	Sarco	Argie (Arg)	Islam	Tausug & Bisaya	Instructor
10.	M	Sattar	Alzad	Islam	Sama, Yakan, Tausug	Professor
Total	6 Female & 4 Male Research Collaborators			9 Muslim & 1 Christian		GO, NGO, Academia

Data Analysis and Data Interpretation

Data with thick description from research collaborators are coded, from which concepts arise and meanings emerge. Ideas are strung together to tell a story from which a middle-range grounded theory develops. Best practices and lessons learned can provide food for thought for other social contexts. I am an Asian male committed to feminism and gender equality, as evidenced in my extensive research and publications.

As the writer of this research paper, I co-construct knowledge with my research collaborators. My positionality as a feminist secular Biocentric Chinese-Filipino male researcher of Buddhist-Christian-Confucian-Taoist heritage who has lived, studied, and worked in Asia, Western Europe, and the U.S.A., colors my interfaith dialogue, inter-ethnic relations, co-production of knowledge, and data interpretation.

FINDINGS

Based on interviews with the research collaborators, the major findings in this paper regarding the relationship between gender and peacebuilding are the following: (1) the context of armed conflict; (2) the impact of armed conflict on women; (3) barriers to women's full participation; (4) the roles women play in peacebuilding; (5) case studies; and, (6) best practices and lessons learned. This section presents these findings.

The Context of Armed Conflict

Historical Roots. While the armed conflict between government troops and different Muslim rebel groups on the surface is **territorial**, its roots are deeper (Diang). The indigenous peoples had kings and rajahs, while the Muslims had sultanates, all of which were decentralized local kingdoms in what is now called the Philippines. Spanish **colonialism**, U.S. colonialism, and post-colonialism changed all that (Guro). The indigenous and Muslim histories “are missing in the national narrative” for which reason the “indignation that Moros [and indigenous peoples] feel... against the Manila-centric government is definitely justified” (Guro).

Economic Inequality and Discrimination. The conflict situation in Mindanao and Sulu Archipelago is rooted in economic inequality, **discrimination** and the need to achieve **self-actualization**. The creation of the Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao was meant to correct the structural problems. However, mass poverty remains to be a major problem (Martin).

Armed Groups and Clan Feuds. The two major Muslim-led armed groups, MNLF and MILF, were formed in response to assert the right to self-determination. Another armed group is the Abu Sayaf Group, particularly in Sulu and Basilan. In the entire Philippines, the New People's Army (NPA) of the underground Communist Party of the Philippines (CPP) under the umbrella of the National Democratic Front (NDF) also operate in Mindanao. The NDF-CPP-NPA struggle against imperialism, bureaucrat or crony capitalism, and semi-feudalism on the national level (Sison, 2014). In addition to that, there are clan feuds, called “rido.” “Election-related violence, land disputes, theft, killing, and murder are the major causes of rido” (Sarco).

Continuing Armed Conflict. The armed conflict has been going on for “more than 40 years” (Sattar), so much so that it has caused untold suffering, especially as the root causes of the armed conflict have not been addressed. “Innocent civilians suffered a lot and the good relationships between Muslims and Christians have deteriorated” (Sattar). “The [armed] conflict...hampers the daily lives of the people, the conflict situation is a threat to the security. Children are so much affected, and civilians caught and die in the crossfire. Those who do not die in the crossfire

die in the evacuation centers for lack of support. They are living in fear and uncertainty, they are unable to attend classes. The conflict contributes to the growing number of illiterates among the people in the conflict areas. The people are dislocated from their homes, thus facing impoverished situation. The Peace accord calls for ceasefire. The conflict temporarily stops, the people go back to their places of origin, homeless, devastated, starting their lives all over again. The peace negotiations is taking too long, sometimes people are no longer interested, they just wanted to recover from the devastation of the conflict, they wanted to restore their properties and wanted to have a normal peaceful life in the communities, they children are back to school and they can work safely in their farms.” (Kanakan).

Peace talks and peace accords come and go. As long as the economic, social, and cultural conditions of the Bangsamoro do not improve, there is no guarantee that the people in Mindanao or Sulu Archipelago will not resort to armed conflict again. “The conflict situation in Mindanao is getting worse. There were several negotiations and peace agreements made by both parties, the GPH and the MNLF & MILF. Yet in the implementations of the programs and the establishment of the Autonomous Regions for Muslim Mindanao failed to meet its objectives to develop, to make the Moro regions progressive as basic requirement for the people to be contented economically, socially and culturally progressive as Bangsamoro” (Ladjajagais).

Peace Process. According to Sattar: “The recent peace accord between the MILF and the Government, however, helped in pacifying the conflict.” Atar noted that on March 27, 2014, the Moro Islamic Liberation Front and the Government of the Philippines signed the Comprehensive Agreement on the Bangsamoro (CAB), incorporating all the agreements and other documents entered into and agreed upon by the parties (MILF and GPH) from the start of the peace talks on January 1997 up to the CAB signing. This new autonomous political government called Bangsamoro, when approved by Congress, will replace the ARMM. Sattar recommends that the Bangsamoro Government “should continue what the present ARMM administration has been doing in reforming the region socially, politically, and economically.”

Positive Impact of BBL. According to Atar, “there are four positive impacts of the BBL: (1) peaceful settlement of conflict in Bangsamoro Homeland; (2) the political leverage that is gained from the international community, through the international observers through the International Contact Group (ICG); (3) the recognition of the Bangsamoro identity; and (4) the granting of the New Autonomous Political Governance which is the ministerial system or parliamentary form of government. This is a new political development in Philippine political history that presidential and parliamentary systems operate under one democratic government.”

Reasons to Rejoice. There are those who are optimistic about the peace deal. Sarco said: “Now, we are happy that the government and the MILF once again came together for another chapter of peace negotiation, we believed that with this peace accord and now were given the way continue our prayers that peace will now on us. This peace accord will bring us into more development, progress and opportunity for everybody because they said this peace accord is for everybody (inclusive as they said).”

Reasons to Worry: However, there are also those who are pessimistic about the peace accord. The term Bangsamoro itself is problematic. Dino commented: “One of the problems arises in the peace process in Mindanao and Sulu archipelago is the use of the identity BANGSAMORO. Not everyone would like to be called “Bangsamoro”. Another problem is that the peace process is not inclusive by not having other groups to be included in the peace process, like the MNLF and other peace movements for self-determination.”

The MILF entered into a peace deal and the MNLF and other Muslim groups are excluded from the agreement. “In Sulu archipelago, the Bangsamoro Comprehensive Agreement or CAB is not fully supported by the locals as there were no consultations have been made before the signing of the said agreement. And the Moro Islamic Liberation Front (MILF) members have never been recognized in Sulu archipelago, especially Jolo Island and Tawi-Tawi, because Sulu archipelago is believed to be the haven of Moro National Liberation Front (MNLF), the mainstream MNLF (Under Nur Misuari’s Leadership/Chairmanship). Although the people are not against peace and the peace process, they just wanted to be heard. Another peaceful group—the Sulu Sultanates Group for Independent Sulu Archipelago—is not included in the peace talk. Sulu archipelago needs to be named in writing, not only mentioning Mindanao to comprise the whole Mindanao and Sulu archipelago (including Palawan). People of Sulu archipelago wanted, at least in the peace process, the full autonomy shall have two entity: Mindanao and Sulu archipelago (the island provinces).”

Dino asserted that “the so-called Bangsamoro is composed of people of very different ethno-linguistic groups who live in different islands. The only thing that binds them together is Islam, but neither geographically nor ethno-linguistically. There are deep differences among the Muslims. “Although Muslims, Mindanaoans are mainly composed of Kagan, Sangil, Maguindanaoan, Maranao, and Iranun; they are not the same as the Sulu archipelago people who are composed mainly of Yakan, Sama-Bajau, and Tausug. These two regions have different culture and traditions as well as languages. Mindanao people speak the same family of languages and Sulu archipelago people understand and speak Bahasa Sug (Sulu archipelago language) with their own dialect; Sama-Bajau and Yakan dialects.”

Dino asked: “Why can’t the current peace talks use the geographical name for the autonomous government like, “Mindanao and Sulu Archipelago Autonomous Government” rather than “Bangsamoro Autonomous Government”? Mindanao and Sulu archipelago Autonomous Government is best enough to be used: at least it will comprise all of the inhabitants of the Mindanao and Sulu archipelago. Every identity and all ethnicities could be preserved and identified, instead of putting everyone in the single identity that is not originally their roots, such as the name Bangsamoro.”

Room for All Imagined Communities. One research collaborator, Anisha Guro, calls for unity in diversity. “Both the Bangsamoro and the Philippine nation are imagined nations. Therefore, there is room for accommodation in both imaginaries... Malaysia and Singapore promote the multi-cultural nature of their respective countries, thereby acknowledging and empowering their minorities... Moros and non-Moros have only been separated by those who converted to Christianity and those who remained Muslims.”

Impact of the Armed Conflict on Women

1. **From Homemaker to Income Earner:** When performing the traditional role of a wife and mother, women have to sacrifice their own needs to attend to the needs of their family members, especially when affected by armed conflict. “We can list down a lot of impacts for all stakeholders. But for women, I guess, it’s quite different. Women in this part of the globe are expected to be good housekeepers (clean the house, attend to the needs of the family, and all house-related chores), be a dedicated wife who attends to her husband’s need, be a good mother, and look out for children, all of which require them to prioritize their need less. And after the conflict, women became more attentive to their kids’ needs (making sure that kids will not be afraid to

- go schools, since education is seen as future “weapon” to fight this kind of war, and a safe haven); women helped their husbands (a new role) in earning income for sustenance, making them balance work and family; women, in short, became more altruistic” (Diang).
2. **Stereotyping**: In Philippine society, Muslims are a minority group. When there is conflict, discrimination against Muslims heightens. Women who wear hijabs are unfortunately easy targets of prejudice, finding it difficult to find a job. “Women always bear the brunt of any conflict. Whenever there is conflict, they are the ones forced to find means to support the family because their menfolk are either fighting or forced to hide or are martyred. When Muslims become equated with terrorism, it is the women who receive the backlash being very visible with their hijabs” (Guro).
 3. **Widowhood**: According to Sattar: “In any armed conflict, women are adversely affected, personally, socially, including their work. The loss of their loved ones in war would certainly create negative psychological impact upon them. Their children become orphans and their lives will be devastated by the war.”
 4. **Discrimination**: Both female and male Muslims are victims of discrimination. Muslims looking for a job get turned down, once prospective employers find out about their religious identity. Dahlia Martin noted: “Whenever armed conflict happens, our religion being a Muslim is affected. We suffered from discrimination to those people who don’t know the real situation in our place. Sometimes they call us terrorist even though we are not. In terms of work, some of our Muslim brothers and sisters shared their difficulty in finding work. For example, they will apply for a job, then after knowing that he/she is a Muslim, the company will just tell them that the position was filled already. People in communities who suffer in armed conflict are in trauma, losing lives, livelihood, and houses.”
 5. **Family Woes**: Because of armed conflict, many women in Mindanao seek jobs abroad. For women who have loved ones who are victims of human rights violations, they also suffer from potentially being harmed themselves. Women who work abroad leave their families in disarray, as their children become alienated without maternal and even sometimes paternal support as well. Noriam Ladjajagais said: “The most vulnerable sectors that are affected are the women and the children. During calamities or man-made calamities such as war, or armed conflict particularly in our province Basilan, the women in general are very much affected because of the responsibilities that they have to take care of the children, the old ones, and the weak people while the conflict is going on. The women are affected physically, emotionally, psychologically and morally. They suffer from fear of being harmed, abused (sexually, physically, morally and emotionally) and even get killed or seeing their loved ones being victims of human rights violations and deprived of their basic needs to survive as human beings with dignity and values in the absence of peace and orderliness. Such that women are forced to work outside of the country to be able to give the basic needs of their children and relatives. Which not all of them are successful, because while they are earning outside of the country, leaving their children with their relatives, children in school are misguided without parents to take care of them. I have many cases of high school students who are affected by the situation where mothers are out and fathers are not around too. Their education which is their future is very much affected.

- Economically, morally, psychologically, socially and physically they are very much affected by the armed conflict in our province and in Mindanao as a whole.”
6. **Pregnant Women and Indigenous Peoples:** When armed conflict occurs, everyone in general is equally affected. But pregnant women have an added concern due to their medical condition. Kanankan stated: “The women are similarly affected ... in the evacuation centers, they are in a difficult situation, especially pregnant and those who have just gave birth.... They are prone to deaths in the evacuation centers, they contribute to the mortality rate of the evacuees during armed conflict..... Among the Indigenous Communities- during evacuations as a result of a violent conflict situation, the IPs do not join the evacuation centers provided for the civilians or the Moro/Maguindanaons, they wanted a separate evacuation center exclusive for the IPs, because even during conflict situations, the IPs are marginalized in terms of the delivery of basic services. Most of the time, they are neglected in terms of delivery of services, it is for this reason that this agency has its own approach in the delivery of basic services during conflict situations.”
 7. **Human Rights in General and Criminality:** The human rights of the people in general, both women and men, are affected by armed conflict. Atar commented: “Peace and security issues in Mindanao and ARMM in particular impacted the lives of the people, including the violation of human rights, such as the right to decent life, security, dignity, education, justice, basic services, and other human rights. On the other hand, the macro and micro levels of violence have tremendous impact on our daily lives, including but not limited to the proliferation of guns, political and domestic killings, kidnap for ransom, and syndicated and armed organized criminals called ‘liangan.’ Some are motivated to join private armed groups, deal in illegal drugs, and engage in illegal logging. People become susceptible to vote buying, migration to other urban areas due to poor economic opportunities and infra development and low level of trust in the formal system. All of these are hurdles to socio-economic, political, and spiritual development among the Mindanawans, particularly the Muslim communities that need to be addressed in order to establish peace and order in our communities.”
 8. **Separation from Family:** When armed conflict strikes, women leave their homes so that they can look for a job to support their children, especially if their husbands have joined the rebel movement. They become the primary income earners. Dino remarked: “Armed conflicts denied the access of farmers to plant their crop and raise their livestock because of the military operations. Women can no longer teach their children properly, as their husbands are joining the groups to fight with the military. The choice they can make is to go to small towns and live with the people, while their husband can no longer work for a proper gainful livelihood to help them. Most of the women are the ones working for the families. Some husbands will only be involved in politics.”
 9. **Economic Burden:** With armed conflict, the cost of basic goods increases. In the Philippines, women in general take care of the family budget and this price increase puts a toll on women’s concerns. In addition, when armed hostilities happen, no one, including women, for their safety, can go to work. Sarco observed: “Armed conflict has always a negative and devastated impact on women, we know the fact that women are more vulnerable to conflict. Economically speaking it leads to increase

price of the basic commodities that become a burden for them because they were the one to take charge of budgeting in the family. When there is armed conflict, we live in the evacuation center and members of the family is easily to acquire a disease due to the absence of proper hygiene. Women can't go their work whether in office, schools or even in farm doing a farming.”

Barriers to the Full Participation of Women

1. **Traditional Men's Role**: In general, men in the Philippines are expected to be the sole breadwinner, although this phenomenon is changing. But religious beliefs have placed some rules on the social roles of women and men. Diang noted: “Traditionally, men are the sole provider for the family but, nowadays, women who are helping their husbands to earn more is a welcome change into that traditional practice. Women and men complement in various works, especially, in the family. There are more women in the political arena as well. However, in line with our religious beliefs, men ought to be leaders and women are seen complement partners whose function is to support men and not to dominate men. Men feel inferior when a woman initiates a particular effort which, I guess, is a challenge for women. Women are ought to do something without “touching” the ego of the men. And people invest a lot of things to protect one's ego or pride in this area.”
According to Sattar, men usually do all the negotiations: “In a Muslim dominated culture, women are not involved in negotiations in any conflict, be it family, community, and group conflict. Men usually do all the negotiations or reconciliations. With the advent of the women's rights advocates, women are now involved to some extent but in limited capacity. Most of their involvement are more of NGOs or government led advocacies rather than personal or family conflict.”
2. **Haram**: There are some religious practices that put a limit on the actions of women, although some of these practices are changing. Dahlia Martin said: “Being a Muslim woman, we are not allowed to go out alone. Only men are doing the grocery and marketing. Muslim women are also not also allowed to talk to men because of the notion of “*Haraam*” or forbidden to socialize with men. Now as time changes, we can do groceries, marketing and shopping. Some become lawyers, politicians and mediator of peace in conflict ridden areas.”
3. **Situationality**: Traditionally, there are some roles that only men can play among Muslim Filipinos. However, there are also some powerful roles that only women can play, such as women who have the honorific title of *Bae A Labi*. Atar observed: “It is situational. There are cases that only men are effective, while there are cases also that both are effective. The traditional leaders such as *Bae A Labi* and other important titles in our clan and community have highest credibility and integrity. Conflicting parties cannot easily refused the women on the mode of settlement made by women mediators”
4. **Changing Times**: Dino stressed that times have changed and practices have changed too in the Philippines. For instance, women can get jobs more easily than men now. He sees a lot of opportunities for women's active involvement in public life.
5. **Men's Lead**: There is a tension between Islam and the secular law of the land. On the one hand, Muslim women avoid holding positions of leadership when men are

- around. On the other hand, the Philippine Constitution calls for the separation of religion from affairs of the state. With gender-sensitive programs, women can overcome hurdles to their full participation in society. Argie Sarco stressed: “As far I know in Islam, women are refraining from holding top and sensitive position or leadership when there are still men in the community. But this is practically not applicable in the Philippines, due to the constitutional provision on the separation of church and state. This serve as a limitation or obstacle. With the strong Gender and Development program institutionalized in all government institution there is no reason that women should not be able to play the roles that men play in society.”
6. **Lack of Awareness:** One hindrance to the full participation of women in public affairs is the lack of information about the rights of women in Islam. To overcome this situation, a Muslim women’s group was formed to educate not only Muslim women but Muslim men and religious leaders as well. Noriam Ladjajagais narrated: “Our NISA group (“women” in Arabic term) started as small group in our respective province in the early 90s. We found out a lot of Moro women are not aware of their Islamic rights. Hence, a lot of them are abused by their husbands or male relatives because of their ignorance of their basic human rights in Islam. So, our small group in our respective province decided to organize into a network of Muslim Women in the Philippines working for the same cause for the betterment of the Moro women especially those who are not fortunate enough to go to school or acquire higher formal education. Our group NISA which was organized formally and officially in the late 2000 is now very much active in educating all women coming from the different sectors and even progressive Muslim men and religious leaders in Islam have been trained on the Islamic rights of Muslim women, which before only the religious men or *ustadjes* know, but do not educate the Muslim women on their rights, instead they just educate them to be submissive to men by telling the women of their Islamic obligations and duties minus their Islamic rights as women in Islam.”
 7. **Education as a Way Out:** In the past, only Muslim men in the Philippines were educated, which was a hindrance to women’s full participation in society. Now, however, more and more Muslim women are have higher education degrees. Anisha Guro emphasized: “Education used to be a privilege and a risk reserved for the Moro men. Nowadays, it is the Moro women who are more aggressive in seeking education. Moro women still fall under the traditional courses known to them, although, the proverbial glass ceiling is being broken as women seek higher education and take courses which were not encouraged to them before.”

The Roles Women Play in Peacebuilding (Shorthand for “Everything” from Negotiation to Reconstruction)

1. **Negotiating Table and Education:** A Muslim woman whose family was once internally displaced by armed conflict is now a Congresswoman. She represents the women’s sector at the negotiating table. At the same time, she gives talks and spreads the word about the peace process to university students. According to Sarah Diang: “Women sit at the negotiating table and represent the women sector. They get invited to talk about the effect of conflict in their respective areas. Most women who are in politics are sending students, whose family experience armed-conflict, into colleges and universities as scholars. Example of these women is current Congresswoman Bai

Sandra Sema who is very passionate about her active participation in the peace process being one of the kids, during her time, whose family experienced to be internally displaced during the 1980's. Congresswoman Sema has hundreds of student-scholars in the university where I am currently connected with. This woman is investing on education and believe that education will make today's generation of young leaders will lead the next generation into a more sustainable peace and order and development."

Sattar gave a concrete example about the role of women: "Generally, women could play a vital role in peacebuilding and reconstruction if given the chance. The Bangsamoro Transition Commission (BTC) for instance has women commissioners who are involved in breaking the MILF-Government peace accord to fruition. And, it was proven successful because the result of that commission is the BBL. On the other hand, women could also actively in calling both conflicting sides to end the war and atrocities especially those involved in peace advocacies through NGOs."

2. **Mostly Invisible But Some Prominent Roles**: Research has shown that many ordinary Muslim women in Mindanao acted as peace builders. However, word is not spread about the active role of Muslim women in peacebuilding, thereby making them invisible. Despite this shortcoming, some prominent Muslim women are known for role in the negotiating panel between the MILF rebels and the government. Anisha Guro cited some examples: "Moro women had always been adept at negotiation and conflict resolution. It is a skill that they have learned from their forebears. The Darrangen is replete with examples of Meranao women settling conflicts among protagonists and thereby preventing further bloodshed. Peace-building is in the psyche of the Moro women, only that it is not recognized by the public. Anne-Marie Hilsdon documented Meranao women's peace-building efforts and these are ordinary Moro women who do not hold government positions. Their role however is not recognized by the public. In the public sphere, Moro women have become members of the negotiating panel between the government and the MILF and these are NCMF Secretary Yasmin Busran Lao, for the government panel and MILF consultants Atty. Raissa Jajurie and Bai Cabaybay."
3. **A Catholic Nun for Peace and Justice**: A Muslim research collaborator, Dahlia Martin, once worked with a Roman Catholic nun until the latter passed away. Martin remembers the powerful and important role that the nun played in organizing and empowering grassroots women to become peace builders and change agents. Dahlia Martin remembered: "The best specific person I can share is Sr. Soledad Perpnan. I admired her in giving peace workshops in the conflict areas. She used the concept of Paolo Freire's Conscientizing Inquiry. We travel in Mindanao to give peace workshops and trained the grassroots women to become peace builders and agents of change."
4. **Dialogue and Mutual Assistance**: Muslim women at the grassroots level themselves to form a support group, assisting members of the group as well as others in times of need. Ladjajagais remarked: "Women are the hearts or the light of every home. Since they are the sectors that are very much affected, they can negotiate individually with their relatives or husbands who are sympathizers or directly involved with the armed groups. Identifying these women are very easy and have dialogue with them, then

- later involved them in a values formation activities and conduct training for their livelihood, so they would be able to live a peaceful and socio-economically progressive life. At the time of conflicts several NGOs came to the areas, but our Muslim women group informally organized ourselves to be able to help each other and the rest of the women in the community that need to be helped by us, not necessarily in the financial aspect but in the moral, psychological, and spiritual aspects in order to make them strong and empowered Moro women.”
5. **High-Level Representation**: Women are properly represented at the negotiating table, along with indigenous peoples, said Fatima Kanakan: “Women and Indigenous Peoples are given special attention during the negotiations, they are properly represented in all mechanisms of the negotiations. For instance, the Government Panel is chaired by a woman and another woman representative as Panel Member. In this sense, the issues and concerns of women are given priority and consideration. In the creation of the Bangsamoro Transition Commission, women are properly represented both in the MILF and GPH members, thus, the issues pertaining to women are properly addressed.”
 6. **Domestic Issues**: For domestic problems, Muslim women in Mindanao traditionally play an important role in conflict resolution. According to Atar: “In our culture, women are deeply respected. There are many instances that negotiation cannot be handled by men especially if the domestic cases are related to gender offenses. In that case women are practically more effective than men during negotiation.”
 7. **Economic Rehabilitation and Education**: When armed conflicts end, women are effective in making sure that their children are educated and their family budget is in order. Hence, women should be involved in planning and putting into place recovery and reconstruction efforts. Nelso Dino insisted that “women should be involved in the reconstruction and reconciliation as they are mostly the one that understood the status of their family problems in the households and they more knowledgeable of the domestic issues, include budgeting and teaching the children at home.”
 8. **GOs and NGOs**: Women are equally effective in playing key roles in government in the peace process or as NGO representatives. Argie Sarco confirmed: “Women play important roles in negotiation, reconciliation, peace building, and reconstruction as key actor, as a monitoring or even as part of the negotiating peace panel, technical working group. In the NGOs women are very important in performing their task in the community.”

Case Studies of Female and Male Research Collaborators Engaged in Peacebuilding Peacemaking, Conflict Resolution, and Negotiation.

1. **High-Level Consultation and Drafting of Organic Act**: Some Muslim leaders asked a research collaborator, Noriam Ladjajagais, for advice and the latter was also involved in drafting the organic law of the Autonomous Region of Muslim Mindanao. Hence, she was directly involved in a high-level capacity both indirectly and directly. Ladjajagais said: “Personally I was not involved, but through consultation of ideas by some Moro leaders who sought our little assistance in dialogue I was able to contribute in my own little way. In fact, I was one of the commissioners who drafted the organic act for the ARMM. But, because of corrupt officials who ran the autonomous regions, the good provisions in the organic act were never implemented. We just hope

and pray that the incoming Bangsamoro Entity will be successful in the implementations of its BBL and in running the Bangsamoro Entity.”

2. **Indigenous People:** Access to justice is important. The justice system includes formal, informal, and traditional justice system, including the regular courts, the Philippine Commission on Human Rights, the Council of Elders, paying “goodwill” or “blood money.” Fatima Kanakan narrated: “In popularizing alternative dispute resolution mechanisms that is recognized by the regular courts to lessen the number of cases filed in the regular courts and as part of the mandate of this Office in resolving conflicts on the community level, there had been a number of cases that were resolved using traditional approach in the resolution of conflicts. This approach lessens the number of cases that are submitted before it. Actual case: Killing of a 20 year old Teduray. Facts of the Case: A killing happened in one of the barangays (village) in the municipality of South Upi, Province of Maguindanao sometime in 2003. In that incident, it was not known who was the real culprit, however, the parents of the victim filed a case against a military personnel and ten members of the CAGU (Civilian Armed Forces Geographical Unit) a para military wing, who were at the same time members of the ethnic Teduray community in that area. The family believed that the military personnel and his men who were members of the CAGU were the last person who apprehended the man, 20 years of age, and an IP villager. Cases were filed before the regular court in the City of Cotabato and a corresponding warrant of arrest was issued. Similar case was filed before the Philippine Commission on Human Rights. The Commanding Officer of the Unit, where the said men belong, found possible means in settling the case by way of submitting it with the Council of Elders of the ethnic tribe. Ground works were made, the Council of Elders were convened, both the complainant and the “suspects” were provided “lawyers” during the course of the deliberations until the issue on the “blood money” or they call it “goodwill money” were discussed. The goodwill money are corresponding to the damages incurred as a result of the loss of the family member. Until such time that the parties agreed as to the extent of the amount to be paid, the victim’s family then agree to sign the affidavit of desistance and eventually dismissed the case in court. These are some examples where a case may be subjected to the agreement of the parties in terms of satisfying the amount of damages incurred, with the possibility that a case might be dismissed.”
3. **Clan Feud:** Clan feuds among Muslims in and from Mindanao can escalate into physical violence, including killings. Both Atar and Sattar have been involved in mediating and solving clan feuds. Sultan Hamidullah Atar is always involved in resolving the conflicts between clans, locally called “rido,” considering that this is his profession as the executive officer of an organization called Rido, Inc. When asked if he is involved in peacemaking or conflict resolution, he replied: “Always. For the past 6 years, I have been involved in the actual resolution of 215 rido cases. I involved different partners both formal and informal state actors especially the clan elders” (Atar).

Sattar was also involved in resolving conflicts between clans: “I have an opportunity to get involved in negotiating between the two major political clans in Basilan province... The conflict started politically and aggravated into a persona one.” A congressman was murdered through bombing in the Batasan (Legislature) Complex in Quezon City, Metromanila. One side to the conflict asked the Basilan Ulama supreme

Council to form a negotiating team to help the two families reconcile, among the team members were the chair, the executive director, and Sattar as secretary-general. The other side to the conflict also formed a negotiating panel. Through “shuttle negotiations,” the reconciliation succeeded after “six months” with the signing of a covenant in front of “the governors of the five provinces of ARMM and some mayors.”

4. **Micro Conflict at School:** As an administrator, Prof. Argie Sarco has been involved in solving the conflicts between students or between students and teachers. “I have personally played a role in negotiation in conflict situation in our school where conflicts involves student against student, student against teacher. I call it as micro conflict. I am happy that we can manage to solve it because we always derive a solution through amicable settlement. We are taken for granted in set aside this conflict because there is a great possibility that it becomes a macro conflict because of the participation of parents, relatives, and other members of the family that turns into rido [or clan feud].”

Reconciliation. At least three of the research collaborators are involved in interfaith dialogue. Others try to settle the conflicts in the school or feuds between clans.

1. For example, Dr. Susana Anayatin organizes “The Celebration of Mindanao Week of Peace” from November 27 to December 3, 2014.
2. Noriam Ladjagais was involved in the reconciliation efforts in the **school**. As a guidance counselor and coordinator, she settled cases of differences between Moro students and among students which involved the parents.
3. Sultan Hamidullah Atar is actively involved in trying to reconcile **feuding families** and clans, using traditional mechanisms.
4. Professor Argie Sarco is engaged in reconciliation work through his involvement with the **interfaith council of leaders** where they emphasize the culture of dialogue.
5. Dr. Alzad Sattar joins interfaith gatherings and pray for peace not only in the southern Philippines but also in other parts of the world, including especially in the Middle East.

Peacebuilding.

1. Diang argued that Mindanao is still at the stage of peacemaking. It is not yet appropriate to talk about peacebuilding: “We believe that Peacebuilding is such an **elusive** term for now. The reason for this is that we are still on the process of Peacemaking which is shortly followed by Peacekeeping, then Peacebuilding. However, I believe that there are efforts made that may qualify as peacebuilding efforts by people who have access on it” (Diang).
2. Ladjagais is in involved in a “**Culture of Peace**” activities for the youth and adults. They have values formation activities to develop the values of peace within the individual persons and to promote peace outside the persons where they learn to reach out for peace and development. All other activities in which she is engaged are for peace, environment, development, and progress. She started her engagement for community development in Culture of Peace, the Green movement for the protection of the environment, Gender and Development which is the major advocacy of NISA, and now she is in the commission for the Filipino language, where she uses the different Moro

- languages in the ARMM to promote understanding, peace, protection of environment and good governance and transparency in “Tuwid na Daan” (or the “right path”).
3. Atar’s organization provided **livelihood** projects to conflicting parties so that the conflict is not only resolved but also transformed. On the other hand, he also helped negotiate **inter-marriages** among conflicting parties to sustain the peace and covenant established both the feuding families.
 4. Dino is personally involved in peacebuilding: his **arts, writings** and knowledge of historical backgrounds of the place, culture and youth-civic programs helped him to contribute something to broaden the understanding of the people.

Recovery Efforts.

1. Diang was a part of a volunteer group from a non-profit organization and they conducted a **community organizing** activity and introduced a **rehabilitation and livelihood** program. There are hundreds of organizations in Mindanao which works similarly and complementarily, Diang stressed.
2. Sarco, through his involvement with the Interfaith Council of Leaders (IFCL), has assisted in the recovery efforts in a certain **community** or barangay where conflict happened. They did not stop after conflict was settle, but continued organizing a dialogue, as well as provided **assistance**, and monitoring the situation until they will back to normal condition. They also assist in providing **trauma healing** for the victims of conflicts, especially women (Muslimah) and children.

Reconstruction. A few research collaborators were involved in reconstruction.

1. Diang volunteered for a group in working with **internally displaced** group who returned to their community. Their **house** used to have non-relatives as guests who stayed with them for days before the guests went home after the conflict ended.
2. In relation to the macro-conflict between the MILF and GPH, Atar handled peace and rehabilitation and recovery programs, including construction of core **shelter**, installation of **water system, psycho-social activities**, and other activities that help the communities recover.

The Role of Women in General. The jury is out. The research collaborators in this paper suggested many ways that women can play in conflict and post-conflict societies. While some research collaborators argue that gender matters, others insist that gender does not really matter as much as the objective of ending the conflict.

1. **Multiple Roles:** Said Sarah Diang, women are effective as relief workers, but women and men in general work harmoniously to assist groups in need of relief: “Women play various roles in this side of the country: relief provider and distributor, emergency response and assistance, psychosocial aide, negotiator, advocate, mediator, etc. Most health-related tasks are dominated unintentionally by women. But if an area is insecure, with the possibility of armed-conflict arising again, most agencies do not send women to work with affected communities. But in general, both men and women worked together in harmony to help a vulnerable group.”
2. **Negotiator:** Women are effective as negotiators, said Anisha Guro, citing an example: “Women’s involvement in conflict resolution is very crucial, as far as the Meranao society is concerned. Women are respected and honored and when they become leaders and

get involved in conflict resolution, parties involved are more inclined to cooperate than with a male negotiator. For instance, former Governor Princess Tarhata Alonto Lucman was a better and braver negotiator who was able to resolve more and high profile conflict than her male successors.”

3. **Women and Men Together:** Women’s role is important, stressed Dahlia Martin. She added that whether the negotiator is female or male does not matter, as long as the aim is ending conflicts: “Women’s involvement in peace reconciliation and advocacy is of great help. Women have a gift of intuition and carrying her soft being will help in the mediation of conflicts. Well, it doesn’t matter if the person involved in negotiation is a man or woman. The important is, having the heart to resolve the conflict and no vested interest.”
4. **Lead Roles:** Giving a few examples, Noriam Ladjajagais insisted that, in peacemaking, gender matter: “Women’s role really matters. That’s why we have involved women who are lawyers from our group like Atty. Raisa Jadjurie, consultant of MILF and seats in the panel, Atty. Johaira Wahab, Sec. Yasmin Busran, (secretary of NCMF), Ms. Fatmawati (Fachy) Salapuddin and some women. We must remember half of the society is composed of women. If half of the society is deprived of human rights and development, no society will be successful, progressive and be developed” (Ladjajagais).
5. **It Depends.** When asked if it matters if people involved are men or women, Sultan Atar replied: “It depends,” claiming that if the person has the skills and leadership qualities, that person, say, a woman, is the right person for the job.
6. **Schools and CSOs:** “Nelson Dino realized that “teachers and civil society members are mostly the avenue of the women to get involved in the peacebuilding and reconciliation process.”
7. **Contribution:** “Women are courageous and persevering. For me, it is not a matter whether people involved are women or men, as long as they can contribute something that is for betterment not become a liability. With our present trends, I believed women’s involvement specifically matters because they can give something which I think is better than the rest.”

Are There Enough Women Involved in Peacebuilding? Among the research collaborators interviewed, there is a lack of consensus as to the extent to which there are enough women involved in peacebuilding.

1. **Peace Work vs. Political Dynasties:** Anisha Guro asserts that, on the one hand, there are women who are involved in peacebuilding at the grassroots level. On the other hand, there are women who are in high-level public office, not because of their gender, but because of their ties to powerful political families. Guro said: “I believe that there are women involved in negotiation, reconciliation, peacebuilding, recovery and reconstruction at the community level, say among the Moros. However, in the public sphere, there are not enough women because these actions preclude being in public office. There are only few women who become elected into office. Among the Meranao community, women leaders are well-respected although those who get elected manage to win an office not on the basis of their being women but mostly because of their clan machinery to win a seat” (Guro).
2. **Not at the Table:** While there are women at the negotiable table, Dahlia Martin noted that most of the negotiators are still men: “There are not enough women involved in

negotiation, reconciliation and reconstruction. As I observe in the mediation of the government between the MILF, most of them are men” (Martin).

3. **Consultation**: Sultan Hamidullah Atar indicated that women are “not excluded but most of the time, they are consulted.”
4. **Important But Not Enough**: According to Nelson Dino, “there are not enough of the women involved in any peacebuilding and reconciliations, although they are being made as the important partner.”
5. **Yes**: Argie Sarco gave a resounding yes, when asked whether there are enough women in peacebuilding work: “Yes, I believed there are enough women directly involved in negotiation, reconciliation, peacebuilding, recovery, and reconstruction. The chief negotiating peace panel of the Philippine government is headed by women in the person of Prof. Ferrer, the Secretary of Office of the Presidential Adviser of the Peace Process Secretary Deles. Women are not excluded, in fact, in the proposed Bangsamoro Basic Law women are given equal opportunity to participate in the proposed Bangsamoro government by creating their political party for them to be part of the parliament. Women must be treated as partners or major players or change agents or service providers. This is true, in Basilan, we have a lady governor, who is very kind and soft spoken, motherly to all and a widow. We have two lady mayors in a two separates cities, the rest are members of the law making body, others are holding managerial position both in national and local government agencies.”

What Can be Done to Involve More Women in Peacebuilding and Reconstruction?

Whether there are enough women or not involved in peacebuilding. However, there are many ways by which more women can be involved in the process of peacebuilding, among which are the following:

1. **Inclusion**: Very importantly, always include women when organizing action groups, said Sultan Hamidullah Atar: “Mobilize the women to include their names during the creation of quick response team, committee on peace and order councils at the same time, involved them in actual negotiations.”
2. **Training**: Dahlia Martin said that “there is a need to train more young women and educate them in negotiation and recovery.”
3. **Holistic Approach**: Anisha Guro said that: “there should be a proactive group/machinery that should be put in place whose goal would be to train, encourage and support women to get involved in peacebuilding and reconstruction. It should be a combination of indigenous and Western knowledge to come up with a holistic approach. The women’s empowerment campaign should include a tangible and achievable goal particularly for the minority women to gauge whether such strategy is working” (Guro).
4. **Motivation and Training**: According to Noriam Ladjajagais: “There are enough women, they just need to be motivated and trained. My group can do that.”
5. **Old Formulas Won’t Work**: Nelson Dino expressed that “there should direct involvement of women in any negotiations; commission for women in the peace process shall be created, not only put them in the group of men.”

6. **Budget Allocation and Policy Implementation:** Argie Sarco insisted that we should put the money where the mouth is: “Strengthen the Magna Carta for Women and enhance and develop the Gender and Development Program with enough budget allocation.”

Critique of the Role of Women.

1. Negative Critique

- a. **Invisibility:** Muslim women are doing peacebuilding work. But there is not much media coverage. There needs to be efforts to document the work of Muslim women in peacebuilding. Anisha Guro asserted: “What women are already doing is invisible to the public. This should be documented, highlighted and given media mileage. Women’s organization should be the mouthpiece of these women who are not able to do the advertising of their involvement themselves. Effort should be done to find those local stories of women who are doing these work behind the scene. It is high time that a women’s center be created that will not only advance the interests of women as Western women liberation understand them, but also include the unique situation of the Moro women. For instance, exploiting Moro culture’s inherent high regard of women to push Moro women into greater and greater involvement in peacebuilding efforts. Women who are in this particular field of work are not able to show their contribution to the society, either for lack of skills to do the “marketing” themselves or they just do not have the opportunity to have a voice in the business-oriented Philippine media.”
- b. **Men:** Noriam Ladjajagais asserts that “the problem is with the men or other factors can come in like the spoilers, who just keep on opposing and criticizing, but not contributing at all for the success of the peace process” (Ladjajagais).
- c. **Inserting Women into Men’s Groups:** If women are only asked to join existing groups composed of men, women’s participation will be nil and the formula does not work, said Nelson Dino: “Women are only put in the group of men to discuss matters. Women are not being heard directly when they are included to discuss matters in the group men. Women will not be speaking much if they put together in a group of men to discuss matters.”

2. Positive Critique

- a. **Active Participation:** Noriam Ladjajagais noted that “as far as the women of my group are concerned, they are very active and vocal. My women’s group NISA headed by Atty. Raisa always make a report and orient us on the progress of the talk. Our women group are more active when it comes to information dissemination and consultation of issues on the ground. We see to it that our interest as women are protected.”
- b. **Civil Society Organizations:** Dahlia Martin observed that as far as women who are involved in peacebuilding are concerned, “most of them become a researcher and writing proposals for peace projects.”
- c. **Does Gender Matter?** When asked if gender matters, Sultan Hamidullah answered: “It depends on the charisma and features or characteristics of women.

If she devoted and committed to help conflict mediation and resolution, thus she has effective outcomes.”

In What Other Areas Should Women be Involved? There are many other ways in which women can be involved in the whole process of peacebuilding.

1. **Media Blitz:** Anisha Guro insisted that Muslim women must treat mass media as a tool to inform society about their work to promote peace. She said they need to “promote their contribution to the public through media coverage, social network, or book launching. The public does not know that Moro women are doing their part in peacebuilding as only the war in Mindanao and its ugly effects are often reported by media.”
2. **Basic Needs and Livelihood:** Dahlia Martin listed several areas which need attention to assist women in situations of armed conflict: “Provision of sustainable livelihood projects to women in conflict ridden areas; access to employment and infrastructure; and, access to water and toilet sanitation.”
3. **All Fields:** Noriam Ladjajagais insisted that women must be involved in practically all fields in government agencies: “Women must be involved in all agencies, since we are half of the society, such as in Education, Health, Housing, Agriculture & fishery, Economic and trade, Governance/ Politics, Military, Environment, and other agencies where women can be accommodated to balance Gender and Development.”
4. **Relief from Tension:** Sultan Hamidullah claimed that as far as women are concerned, “they are very effective during preventing period; meaning, when the parties are not yet done with retaliation, the women have big role for counseling and giving inputs to calm the situation.”
5. **Livelihood:** Nelson Dino looked at the rice-and-fish issues confronting women, exclaiming that women must have the opportunity to be involved in “budgeting, social building, and social entrepreneurship.”
6. **Multi-Function:** For Argie Sarco, women can play roles to “promote the Culture of Dialogue, focusing on capacity building; network with other stakeholders; utilize the available resource for the purpose; and adopt multi effective strategies on negotiation and reconciliation.”

CONCLUSION

Summary

The armed conflict in the southern Philippine islands of Mindanao and Sulu Archipelago has been waging for decades. There have been peace talks but the final cessation of armed hostilities is elusive, especially if the deeply-rooted structural problems are not addressed and solved. Armed conflict disproportionately impact women, as they frequently take on new roles and become the new sole breadwinner, especially if their spouses join the rebel movement or die as a result of combat. The greatest barrier to women’s participation in peacebuilding and reconstruction is tradition: the tradition that men play certain roles, mostly in the public sphere, and women play only certain roles, mostly in the domestic sphere. However, as times change, new traditions are likewise created, included the “new masculinities,” which call for equal sharing of responsibilities between women and men in both the public and private spheres. This paper presented case studies of women and men who talked about the role of women in peacebuilding. Men

shared their personal involvements in peacebuilding to provide the readers a comparative analysis of the possibilities for peacebuilding work for both women and men.

Implications of Best Practices and Lessons Learned for Practice

From the literature review, we learned lessons and best practices. We learned that there are three models of the role of gender in peacebuilding: (1) gender-blind, (2) gender-sensitive, and (3) gender-relational. There are power relations and we need to change the power relations for gender equality. Therefore, including women in peacebuilding and reconstruction is a choice. It is intentional. Instead of viewing all women as victims and all men as aggressors, we need to work towards new masculinities in which men learn to share responsibilities both at home and in the public sphere. Women and men need to work together everywhere.

However, we must not limit ourselves to gender mainstreaming only, which is necessary but not sufficient. We must see the intersectionality of class, gender, age, generations, literacy, culture, religion, abilities, and other differences and ensure the social inclusion of all in the peacebuilding efforts. People who are illiterate or less literate, people who are poor, people of different social status, internally displaced persons, and people of other differences in the local communities must have the same opportunities not only to be invited to organize or join groups but also to take on leadership roles.

From the literature and from the case studies cited in this research, there are also best practices and lessons learned. We learned that there are many different kinds of violence: personal, family, inter-family or inter-clan, criminal, political, structural, and more. We need to deal with all kinds of violence. To do so, there is a need to dig deep, examine historical roots, enter into dialogue, and solve the deeply-rooted problems in order to bring about genuine and durable peace. Access to formal, informal, traditional, and customary justice system is important.

Implications of Lessons Learned and Best Practices for Policy

From the best practices and lessons learned, we assert that women must not be seen as “vulnerable” but as active change agents. In conflict and post-conflict situations, women must have the opportunity for political advancement and economic advancement. Women must have the equal opportunity to work both in the private and public domains and take leadership roles in the economic, political, social, cultural, legal, domestic, and all other spheres the way men do. In order to do so, budgets and funds must be allotted to make women play active roles in peacebuilding and reconstruction a reality. Furthermore, there must be numerous opportunities for women to participate in education and training programs so that they can gain much needed new skills needed for their leadership roles.

Note, however, that when structural violence, such as mass poverty and injustice, is not eradicated, armed conflict looms on the horizon.

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ADDITIONAL RESOURCES

Georgetown University Institute for Women, Peace and Security
<http://giwps.georgetown.edu/>

Insights on Conflict: Peacebuilding and gender/women
<http://www.insightonconflict.org/themes/gender-womens/>

Insight on Conflict: Peacebuilding gender/women: resource guide
<http://www.insightonconflict.org/themes/gender-womens/resources/>

Institute for Inclusive Security <http://www.inclusivesecurity.org/>

International Alert
<http://www.international-alert.org/gender>

Peace Women is a project of the Women's International League for Peace and Freedom, United Nations Office www.peacewomen.org

Promundo (Transforming Masculinities)
<http://www.promundo.org.br/en/>

United States Institute for Peace (USIP) Center for Gender and Peacebuilding
<http://www.usip.org/centers/gender-and-peacebuilding-center>

UN Women the United Nations Entity for Gender Equality and the Empowerment of Women
<http://www.unwomen.org>

ACRONYMS

No.	Acronym	In Full
1.	ARMM	Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao
2.	BBL	Bangsamoro Basic Law, abolishing the present autonomous government in Muslim Mindanao
3.	BMA	Bangsa Moro Army
4.	BTA	Bangsamoro Transition Authority
5.	BTC	Bangsamoro Transition Commission
6.	CAB	Comprehensive Agreement on Bangsamoro
7.	CPP	Communist Party of the Philippines
8.	CSO	Civil Society Organizations
9.	FAB	Framework Agreement on the Bangsamoro
10.	GBV	Gender-Based Violence
11.	GOs	Governmental Organizations
12.	GPH	Government of the Philippines
13.	ICG	International Contact Group
14.	MAG	Mindanao Autonomous Government
15.	MILF	Moro Islamic Liberation Front
16.	MNLF	Moro National Liberation Front
17.	NDFP	National Democratic Front of the Philippines
18.	NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
19.	NPA	New People's Army
20.	RP	Republic of the Philippines
21.	SAAG	Sulu Archipelago Autonomous Government
22.	TPMT	Third Party Monitoring Team